

JURISPRUDENCE

EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS JURISPRUDENCE AT THE INTERSECTION OF INDIVIDUAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL JUSTICE: THE CASE LAW CONCERNING ALBANIA

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Abstract

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) significantly influences national legal systems, prompting debate over whether its role is to deliver individual justice or address systemic legal and constitutional issues. Recent procedural reforms, including the prioritization of 'impact cases', and the pilot judgment procedure, reflect a shift toward a more constitutional approach, tackling systemic deficiencies at the domestic level.

This paper investigates the interplay between individual rights and constitutional justice in Albania, with particular attention to relevant ECtHR rulings that have influenced national legislation. The analysis underlines the transformative impact of ECtHR case law on Albania's legal landscape and evaluates the Court's influence on the alignment of domestic laws with international human rights norms, while also addressing the persistent challenges faced in this endeavor. By exploring the evolving role of the Court, this research adds to the ongoing discussion regarding the ECtHR's status within the European legal framework, highlighting its relationship with Albania's domestic legislation.

Keywords: European Court of Human Rights; European Convention on Human Rights; individual justice; constitutional justice; jurisprudence.

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has a profound influence on domestic legal systems within the Council of Europe, prompting discussions about its role not only as an international judicial body but also as one with constitutional functions (Ulfstein, 2021). Court has repeatedly characterized the European Convention on Human Rights (Council of Europe, 1950) as a "constitutional instrument of European public order" (Loizidou v. Turkey, 1995), suggesting that the ECtHR's jurisprudence extends beyond merely resolving individual cases to shaping national legal frameworks. In Albania, the legal status of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) is defined by the country's monist legal system (Omari & Anastasi, 2010). As a monist state, Albania integrates international law directly into its domestic legal order without the need for separate national legislation to incorporate it. According to Article 116 of the Albanian Constitution (*Constitution of Albania*, 1998), the Convention holds a supra-legal position in the hierarchy of normative acts, meaning it is positioned beneath the Constitution but above ordinary laws. This hierarchy ensures that if a national law contradicts the provisions of the Convention, it is considered both unconstitutional and anti-conventional.

Furthermore, Article 5 of the Albanian Constitution explicitly states that the Republic of Albania applies international law that is binding upon it. In terms of limitations on rights and freedoms, Article 17 emphasizes that any restrictions must be established by law, based on the public interest or the protection of others' rights. Importantly, these limitations must be proportional to the situation and cannot violate the essence of the rights provided for in

the Constitution, nor can they exceed the limitations set forth in the European Convention on Human Rights.

Finally, Article 122(2) further affirms the primacy of international agreements in Albania's legal system. It states that any international agreement ratified by law takes precedence over domestic laws that are incompatible with it. This means that Albania is bound by its international obligations, ensuring that the European Convention on Human Rights holds a crucial role in shaping the country's legal landscape and the protection of human rights.

National authorities are legally bound to implement ECtHR judgments under Article 46 of the Convention, yet national courts often extend beyond these obligations by incorporating the Court's broader jurisprudence. This practice reflects a process of constitutionalization, where national courts and the ECtHR function as a unified legal system, with the latter serving as the ultimate interpreter of the ECHR. Consequently, national courts are expected to align their decisions with ECtHR precedents, further embedding ECHR principles within domestic legal frameworks (Ulfstein, 2021,169).

Ulfstein highlights that the ECtHR plays a crucial role in national judicial review, impacting two key areas: first, the relationship between the state and its citizens, where it helps define human rights; and second, the interaction among national constitutional organs. Through its case law, the ECtHR indirectly shapes the review of national legislative or executive actions, fulfilling important constitutional functions (Ulfstein, 2021,157).

Despite being a cornerstone of the international human rights system, the ECtHR faces mounting pressures, including case backlogs and the challenge of

legal harmonization across diverse national contexts. Thus implicate structural questions that concern the very nature and *raison d'être* of the Convention system and its court, also touching upon the old debate on the “individual” versus “constitutional” type of justice rendered by the Court (Kunz, 2018).

Albania serves as a compelling paradigm in assessing the ECtHR's influence on the domestic legal framework. Since it acceded to the Council of Europe in 1995, Albania has been under the jurisdiction of the ECtHR, resulting in a series of decisions that have influenced its legal framework. The interplay between individual rights and constitutional justice is particularly evident in Albania, where ECtHR judgments have prompted legal reforms to align domestic laws with ECHR standards. Despite this progress, persistent challenges hinder full compliance with ECtHR rulings, revealing systemic issues that complicate the enforcement of human rights protections at the national level. This study examines the impact of ECtHR jurisprudence on Albania's legal landscape, evaluating both advancements and ongoing difficulties in upholding human rights and constitutional principles.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

This article employs a qualitative legal analysis to examine the relationship between individual rights and constitutional justice in Albania, as reflected in case law. The research is structured around three principal methods:

Case Law Analysis –The HUDOC database has served as a source for relevant case law. Emphasis is placed on cases such as *Xheraj v. Albania*, which illustrate the interactions among the ECtHR, the Albanian Constitutional Court, and the Supreme Court, thereby highlighting the influence of ECtHR jurisprudence on national legislation and constitutional justice. Another pivotal case is the pilot judgment of *Manushaqe Puto and Others v. Albania* regarding a systemic deficiency of the domestic system and its impact on legislative amendments.

Doctrinal Research – This method involves a review of scholarly literature and prior studies on the impact of ECtHR jurisprudence, including its role in shaping both individual and constitutional justice. By evaluating academic perspectives, the research contextualizes Albania's legal advancements within the broader framework of international human rights.

Documentary Review – This includes an analysis of relevant provisions of the European Convention on Human Rights, the Constitution of the Republic of Albania, and other domestic laws, alongside secondary sources such as academic literature. The study conceptualizes the position of ECtHR jurisprudence within the Albanian legal framework. Accordingly, the paper relies primarily on desk research, utilizing ECtHR judgments and the ECHR as primary sources, and academic articles as secondary sources.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. Overview of the ECtHR's Role in Individual and Constitutional Justice

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) is widely regarded as the crown jewel of the world's most advanced international system for protecting civil and political liberties (Hefler, 2008). However, the increased number of states under its jurisdiction, the strong public reputation, its expansive interpretations of individual liberties, and distrust of domestic judiciaries, have contributed to an overwhelming backlog of applications (Hefler, 2008).

Under these conditions, Wildhaber emphasizes that the Court's primary concern is managing its caseload to focus on its constitutional role, which should be limited to fundamental decisions shaping a “European public order” based on human rights, democracy, and the rule of law (Wildhaber, 2002). In other words its primary focus should be on cases of constitutional significance, i.e. cases of principle rather than merely providing justice in individual cases (Ulfstein, 2021, 153).

The debate on the constitutionalization of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has gained significant scholarly attention, with discussions focusing on whether the Court should function primarily as an adjudicatory body providing individual justice or as a quasi-constitutional court shaping broader human rights jurisprudence. The reviewed literature explores this dual role and assesses the extent to which the ECtHR exhibits constitutional characteristics. Scholars debate whether the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) primarily serves as an adjudicatory body providing individual justice or as a quasi-constitutional court shaping broader human rights jurisprudence. Greer and Wildhaber explore these perspectives, arguing that while the Court addresses individual complaints, it also exhibits significant constitutional characteristics.

The individual justice model asserts that the ECtHR's primary function is to redress Convention violations for individual applicants, with whatever constitutional or systemic improvements at the national level might result (Greer & Wildhaber, 2013, p.663). Recourse to an international court offers victims of human rights violations a means of redress that domestic authorities may otherwise deny. However, the Convention guarantees only declaratory, pecuniary, and procedural remedies, without substantive reparations, as outlined in Article 41. More broadly, ‘individual justice’ reflects the Convention system's commitment to ensuring that every genuine victim of a violation receives a judgment in their favor—regardless of the violation's severity, administrative burden, compensation received, or its impact on state conduct or legal practice (Greer & Wildhaber, 2013, p.663). While the individual justice model emphasizes case-specific remedies, Greer and Wildhaber argue that the ECtHR also performs a broader constitutional role. First, in *Loizidou v. Turkey*, the Court explicitly recognized the Convention as “a constitutional instrument of European public order.” They argue that human rights litigation is inherently constitutional, as it concerns the distribution of rights, the limits of public

power, and institutional structures—issues typically handled by supreme or constitutional courts, akin to the ECtHR at the European level.

Secondly, the ECtHR mirrors domestic supreme or constitutional courts, adjudicating similar issues using principles such as democracy, the rule of law, subsidiarity, and proportionality. It assesses whether human rights restrictions are legitimate, legally grounded, and necessary in a democratic society (Greer & Wildhaber, 2013, p.668).

Alec Stone Sweet considers the ECHR a treaty that establishes an international organization, substantive norms, and enforcement procedures, making it "constitutional" in at least a basic sense. With the adoption of Protocol No. 11, the ECHR evolved into a system of constitutional justice, entrenching fundamental rights and ensuring their judicial protection at the request of individuals, making it "constitutional" in a deeper sense (Stone Sweet, 2009, p.2)

Under Protocol No. 11, the ECtHR possesses the formal authority necessary to shape and dominate the Convention system. It holds plenary powers to interpret Convention rights authoritatively and supervise their application within national legal systems. Over time, the Court has developed a dense body of jurisprudence that guides national officials—legislators, executives, and judges—who choose to enhance the effectiveness of Convention norms. However, the impact of its rulings depends on the willingness of domestic authorities to incorporate its interpretations into their legal frameworks (Stone Sweet, 2009, p.4). Despite these constitutional attributes, the ECtHR critically differs from traditional constitutional courts: it lacks the power to invalidate national legal norms contradicting fundamental rights. This limitation on its remedial authority raises a significant objection to classifying the Strasbourg Court as a full-fledged constitutional court (Stone Sweet, 2009, p.7).

Dzehtsiarou and Greene acknowledge the ECtHR's constitutional characteristics but argue that its adjudicatory and constitutionalist functions should remain distinct. They advocate for tailored reforms to optimize the Court's performance in both roles (Dzehtsiarou & Greene, 2013, p.4). To achieve this distinction, they emphasize the importance of identifying constitutionalist issues, which helps distinguish purely adjudicatory cases—those that neither redefine the limits of state power nor resolve conflicting jurisprudence, involve serious human rights breaches, or carry significance beyond the parties involved. Such cases can be decided based on precedent without necessitating further legal developments. Dzehtsiarou and Greene categorize constitutionalist cases into three types. First, cases that present novel legal issues, enabling the Court to delineate the scope of the Convention. Second, cases addressing endemic human rights violations embedded in a state's legal system, require systemic solutions. Third, cases involving severe human rights breaches that threaten a state's commitment to the Convention and, by extension, the legitimacy of the Convention itself.

This distinction between adjudicatory and constitutionalist cases aligns with the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) evolving case-processing strategy. Launched in 2021, the Court's new approach refines its prioritization framework to focus on potentially well-founded "impact" cases—those with broader implications for human rights protection. The strategy emphasizes the adjudication of cases that influence public policy and contribute to the development of the Convention system (ECtHR, 2021). Kohte defines impact cases as those extending beyond the interests of individual applicants to affect the broader Convention community. These recent reforms signal a shift toward a more constitutional approach to justice, reinforcing the ECtHR's role in shaping systemic legal and human rights developments across Europe (Kohte, 2021).

4. THE INTERSECTION OF INDIVIDUAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL JUSTICE OF ECtHR

4.1. Pilot judgment

Constitutionalist issues often emerge from repeated judgments in numerous cases revealing systemic human rights violations in a particular State. When a Contracting Party persistently disregards the Convention and the Court's explicit rulings, it undermines both the effectiveness of the Court in achieving the Convention's objectives and the state's commitment to the European human rights framework (Dzehtsiarou & Greene, 2013).

In response to such systemic deficiencies, the "pilot judgment procedure" is the boldest initiative of the Court (Greer & Wildhaber, 2013). The pilot judgment procedure enables the Court to issue a ruling on an individual application while identifying broader structural issues that require legislative or policy changes (*Manushaqe Puto and Others v. Albania*, 2012).

A striking example is *Manushaqe Puto and Others v. Albania*, which addressed systemic violations resulting from the failure to enforce compensation for former property owners under the Property Acts. This judgment underscored not only individual human rights violations but also persistent legal and administrative shortcomings despite earlier rulings in *Driza v. Albania* and *Ramadhi v. Albania*. The Court noted that these deficiencies contributed to a surge in repetitive applications to Strasbourg, ultimately threatening the integrity of the Convention system (*Manushaqe Puto and Others v. Albania*, 2012, §§104–105).

The Court also stressed the urgency for Albanian authorities to establish an effective compensation mechanism. However, it cautioned against frequent amendments to property legislation—at least seven changes between 2004 and 2010—which created legal uncertainty and inconsistent judicial practices. The Court urged the Albanian government to consider the legal and financial implications before introducing further reforms to ensure stability and clarity (*Manushaqe Puto and Others v. Albania*, 2012, §110).

The pilot judgment mechanism exemplifies the ECtHR's shift from resolving individual cases to implementing broader measures aimed at preventing

future violations. This approach led to the adoption of the 2015 Property Act (Law No. 133/2015), which introduced a new compensation scheme and a property valuation methodology designed to balance property rights with public interest. The law established clear rules for determining and distributing compensation funds within specified time limits. Subsequent amendments included:

Law No. 77/2022: Revised the 2015 Property Act to further streamline the compensation process.

Law No. 111/2018: Focused on cadastre reforms, facilitating the registration of unfinished properties and improving inter-institutional cooperation (Law no. 111, 2018).

Law No. 20/2020: Addressed transitional property-related processes in Albania, aiming to resolve outstanding claims more efficiently (Law No.20, 2020).

4.2. Impact case “Xheraj v. Albania”: Reopening of Criminal Cases Following an ECtHR Judgment

The case of *Xheraj v. Albania* serves as a significant example of the intersection between individual rights and constitutional jurisprudence under the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR). The applicant, Xheraj, complained to the ECtHR, arguing that the Albanian Supreme Court had violated the principle of legal certainty by allowing a prosecutor to appeal a final acquittal beyond the legal time limit (*Xheraj v. Albania*, 2008). This was found to be a breach of Article 6(1) of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), which guarantees the right to a fair trial. As a result, the ECtHR applied Article 41 of the Convention, concluding that reopening the proceedings for *restitutio in integrum* was the most appropriate remedy.

Implementing this judgment required the reopening of criminal proceedings at the domestic level. However, at the time, Albania's Criminal Procedure Code did not include provisions allowing for the reopening of a case following an ECtHR ruling, leading to a jurisdictional dispute between the Constitutional Court and the Supreme Court over the proper interpretation and implementation of ECtHR rulings within the national legal system. The Constitutional Court reviewed the applicant's case and, issued a decision for the Supreme Court to reopen the proceedings, and cautioned against the dangers of disregarding a final and binding decision of the Constitutional Court (Decision no. 22, 2010). Ultimately, the Supreme Court complied, leading to the annulment of the applicant's conviction and its removal from the criminal record, following the ECtHR's ruling (Decision no. 01226/2011, 7 March 2012). This case set an important precedent, prompting legislative changes to ensure the domestic legal system aligned with international human rights obligations (Toska, 2022). Specifically, Article 450(d) of the Criminal Procedure Code was amended to explicitly allow for the reopening of proceedings when an ECtHR judgment finds a violation of fundamental rights, with

requests for retrial required to be submitted within six months of notification (Law No. 7905, 1995).

4.3. The case Dauti v. Albania: Dispute of Jurisdictions

The case of *Dauti v. Albania* highlights issues of access to justice and the enforcement of ECtHR rulings. Dauti challenged the lack of judicial review over Appeals Commission decisions, a claim rejected by Albanian courts as these decisions were deemed final (*Dauti v. Albania*, 2009). The ECtHR ruled in his favor, prompting Albania to amend its laws to allow judicial review of Appeals Commission decisions. As a result, the Law no. 7703, dated 11.5.1993, ‘On social insurance in the Republic of Albania,’ was amended with Law no. 10 447, dated 14.7.2011.

In 2021, the case re-emerged regarding the application of these amendments. The Supreme Court sought Constitutional Court guidance on whether it could disregard national law in favor of the ECHR and whether the revised legislation complied with Dauti's judgment. Specifically, the questions that emerged were:

1. Is the Supreme Court authorized to set aside national law and directly apply the Constitution and international law in a specific case?

2. What is the legal significance of the Committee of Ministers' determination that Albania has implemented the ECtHR ruling, given that the new legislation still does not fully align with ECtHR jurisprudence?

3. Does the amended legislation comply with the Dauti ruling, and does the newly formed commission meet the standards outlined in Article 6 of the ECHR?

The Constitutional Court declined substantive review, leaving the matter to the Supreme Court (Decision no. 55, 2021). The Supreme Court later ruled that the amended law remained inconsistent with ECtHR case law and reaffirmed that national courts must apply the ECHR directly, overriding conflicting domestic provisions (Decision no. 00-2021-1317, 2021). It also found the newly established commission failed to meet ECtHR standards. Consequently, the Court declared conflicting provisions "inoperable" and mandated judicial review of commission decisions (Decision no. 00-2021-1317, 202, §1591). This ruling reinforces the Supreme Court's role in ensuring ECtHR compliance, affirming that national laws cannot override Convention rights.

5.CONCLUSION

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) continues to serve its foundational role as an adjudicator of individual rights, but its jurisprudence increasingly constitutionally influences national legal systems. Mechanisms such as the pilot judgment procedure illustrate the Court's broader governance function by addressing systemic violations and guiding legislative reforms. This shift is further evidenced by the prioritization of impact cases, indicating a move toward a more constitutional role for the ECtHR.

Cases such as *Xheraj v. Albania* and *Dauti v. Albania* highlight tensions between the Constitutional Court and the Supreme Court over the implementation of ECtHR rulings. While national courts are expected to follow ECtHR precedents, disagreements over jurisdiction and legal interpretation have resulted in inconsistencies, complicating Albania's efforts to enforce human rights protections effectively.

Scholars continue to debate whether further institutional reforms are necessary to solidify the Court's constitutional role, or whether a hybrid approach that balances individual justice with constitutional adjudication is the most effective path forward.

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